

MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS OF TOURISM MANAGEMENT COLLEGE STUDENTS: EXAMINING THE ACADEMIC, PERSONAL, AND SOCIAL VARIABLES

Jhonnell J. Abalajon¹, Kirsty G. Tanque², Ginalyn J. Obien¹, Roselyn P. Cabantud¹,
Ramy Lloyd L. Lotilla³, Aiza A. Lizada², Gary L. Llegue², Hyacinth J. Jarencio²,
Jocelyn A. Magallanes¹, Justine L. Deleña²

¹*Hospitality Management Department, Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College,
Philippines*

²*Tourism Management Department, Capiz State University Sigma Satellite College,*

³*Technical Teacher Education Department, Capiz State University, Roxas City, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13889028>

ABSTRACT

This study, titled "Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students," employs a descriptive research design combined with quantitative data analysis to explore the motivations driving students in this field. A total of 266 respondents were randomly selected from a population sample of 216 tourism management students, utilizing both Google Forms and physical surveys. The survey included demographic profiles and motivational factors, with content validity established through expert review. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS software, employing mean scores and percentages for interpretation, while qualitative data underwent thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase approach. The findings reveal a predominantly young, female student demographic, with many from low-income backgrounds and first-generation college families. Motivational factors were classified into relationships, effort, aspiration, cognition, and heart, with aspiration identified as the most significant, reflecting a strong drive toward future goal. Effort and heart also emerged as important, highlighting the influence of external rewards and personal satisfaction. While relationships and cognition were present, they were slightly less dominant. The study indicates that these motivational factors significantly impact students' academic, personal, and social experiences, shaped by environmental influences like online learning and support systems. It underscores the necessity for educational programs to address socio-demographic challenges and enhance career

guidance. Recommendations include targeted financial aid, improved career support, and emotional support systems to bolster student engagement and success in tourism management programs. This multifaceted approach integrates intrinsic aspirations with supportive educational practices to improve overall student outcomes.

Keywords: *Driving Forces, Student Engagement, Career Aspiration, Student Support, Student Engagement, Familial and Community Influences*

INTRODUCTION

In the evolving landscape of education, understanding the motivational factors that influence students' academic, personal, and social experiences is crucial for their success and well-being. This study aims to explore these motivational factors and their relationships with various variables, providing insights that are vital for adapting educational practices to meet the current needs of the country. Historically, research and development (R&D) in education have played a pivotal role in improving educational quality and addressing societal changes. For instance, Ain and Nor (2017) found that motivation and learning strategies are positively correlated with academic performance, highlighting the importance of these factors in shaping students' success. Building on such findings, this study will focus on the specific needs and challenges faced by tourism management students, offering insights that can inform targeted interventions and support strategies.

Furthermore, the results of this study will be invaluable to educators, policymakers, and researchers in the education sector. By shedding light on the factors that motivate students, the study will help develop strategies that enhance educational practices and policies, ensuring that students are supported in their academic, personal, and social development. For example, Wang and Li (2020) emphasized the role of motivation and self-regulated learning in engaging students, underscoring the need to focus on these aspects in educational interventions. Similarly, Cho and Heron (2015) found that motivation and self-regulated learning are significant predictors of academic achievement, further highlighting the importance of these factors in the current educational landscape. In terms of academic variables, these refer to factors that directly influence a student's learning process. Effort is the time and energy a student dedicates to studying and completing tasks. Aspiration reflects a student's goals or ambition for academic achievement, while cognition refers to the mental processes involved in learning, such as memory, problem-solving, and understanding. On the other hand, personal variables pertain to the individual's internal characteristics. Heart (Emotional Engagement) indicates how emotionally invested a person is in their learning or tasks, which can significantly affect their motivation. In this context, aspiration represents the personal dreams and desires that drive someone to achieve more in life. Lastly, social variables involve external influences from other people. Relationships are the connections and interactions with peers, teachers, and family that can impact learning. Additionally, Heart (Emotional Engagement) here refers to the emotional aspect of social interactions,

which influences motivation and commitment through social support or encouragement. By addressing these academic, personal, and social variables, the study aims to provide a comprehensive framework for understanding student success.

The study aimed to determine the motivational factors of tourism management college students by examining the academic, personal, and social variables.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the motivational factors of tourism management college students by examining the academic, personal, and social variables. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of tourism management college students in terms of age, gender, year level, income, and parents' highest educational attainment?
2. What is the level of motivational factors of tourism management college students focusing on relationships, effort, aspiration, cognition, and heart?
3. What is the most dominant motivational factors of tourism management college students?
4. How do motivational factors of tourism management college students influence students' academic, personal, and social experiences?

METHODOLOGY

The research design for the study titled "Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students" utilized a descriptive approach with quantitative data analysis to achieve a comprehensive understanding of student motivation. This design systematically examined the motivational factors and socio-demographic profiles of tourism management students, offering a clear snapshot of their motivation at the time of the study.

The target population comprised 216 tourism management students, and a total of 266 respondents participated, representing first to fourth-year students. A random sampling method was employed to ensure a representative and diverse sample, calculated using Cochran's formula.

Data collection was conducted through a combination of Google Forms and physical surveys. The questionnaire was structured into sections covering demographic profiles and motivational factors. To establish content validity, the questionnaire underwent a review by an English critic and academic experts in both core and minor tourism subjects. Their feedback was instrumental in refining the questionnaire for clarity and relevance.

Quantitative data analysis was performed using SPSS software, where means were calculated to determine average values, and percentages were utilized to present data

distributions. Additionally, qualitative data were analyzed through thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase approach.

The study adhered to ethical research principles by securing informed consent and ensuring anonymity for all participants. An approved letter from the Office of the President was obtained prior to data collection, confirming the study's legitimacy and compliance with institutional protocols. This careful consideration of both methodology and ethics ensured the rigor and relevance of the study in understanding the motivational factors influencing tourism management students.

While the study aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of student motivation, the findings may be limited to the specific population of tourism management students at the selected institution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Demographic Profile of Tourism Management College Students

The socio-demographic profile of tourism management college students reveals important trends and patterns that can help in understanding their educational and motivational needs. The majority of students (82%) fall within the 18-24 age range, indicating a predominantly young student population. Gender distribution shows a high representation of females (83%), with significantly fewer males (14%) and a small number of non-binary and other gender identities. This suggests a gender imbalance in the tourism management program, which could influence group dynamics and support needs. Year-level distribution indicates a relatively even spread, though 1st and 4th-year students represent the largest groups at 33% and 36%, respectively. Income data shows that most students come from lower-income backgrounds, with 78% earning less than ₱10,000, which may impact their academic and personal resources. Educational attainment of parents varies, with a significant number of fathers having only high school education (44%) and many mothers also having high school education (49%). This reflects a potential socio-economic factor influencing students' educational experiences and aspirations.

The data highlights a young and predominantly female student population with a considerable portion coming from low-income families. The educational attainment of parents suggests that many students are first-generation college attendees, which may affect their access to academic support and resources. For instance, the lower parental education levels could be associated with less familiarity with higher education processes and challenges. Additionally, perceiving the value of education is linked to higher academic motivation across different cultural contexts (Eccles & Wigfield, 2020).

Understanding the socio-demographic profile is crucial for tailoring educational support and interventions. The high proportion of low-income students might necessitate financial aid programs, scholarships, and support services to enhance their academic experience. The gender imbalance could prompt the need for gender-sensitive approaches in teaching and student support services. Additionally, the varying

educational backgrounds of parents suggest that increased outreach and guidance might be needed to assist students who may lack familial academic support. Overall, these insights can inform targeted strategies to improve student engagement, support, and success in the tourism management program. Demographic profiles, including age, gender, and socioeconomic status, also play a role in shaping motivational profiles. Motivational profiles may vary across age groups regarding achievement goals and intrinsic motivation (Zheng et al., 2022). Potential variations in academic motivation exist between genders, requiring further exploration (Eccles & Wigfield, 2021). Moreover, a complex relationship exists between socioeconomic status and academic motivation, highlighting the need for understanding both challenges and opportunities to support students from diverse backgrounds (Diemer & McInnis, 2020).

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Profile of Tourism Management College Students

Socio-demographic Profile	N	Percentage
Age		
18-24	218	82%
25-34	48	18%
Gender		
Male	38	14%
Female	221	83%
Non-Binary	1	1%
Others	6	2%
Year level		
1st year	88	33%
2nd Year	13	5%
3rd Year	69	26%
4th Year	96	36%
Income		
Less than 10,000	207	78%
₱10,000 - ₱19,999	45	17%
₱20,000 - ₱29,999	12	4%
₱30,000 - ₱39,999	2	1%
Fathers Highest Educational Attainment		
Elementary	99	37%
Highschool	116	44%
College	39	15%
Graduate Studies	12	4%
Mothers Highest Educational Attainment		
Elementary	41	15%
Highschool	130	49%
College	74	28%
Graduate Studies	21	8%

Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students

Relationship

The data on relationship-related motivational factors reveals that students are highly motivated by setting clear goals and observing progress, as evidenced by the high mean scores for items like “Setting clear and achievable goals motivates me to put in the necessary effort” (M = 4.08) and “Seeing progress made towards my goals increases my desire to learn and study” (M = 4.10). This aligns with Ryan and Deci’s (2017) assertion that goal-setting and progress are integral to fostering intrinsic motivation. The grand mean of 3.95 supports the notion that maintaining a balance between academic efforts and handling coursework pressures is crucial. However, challenges such as balancing multiple commitments can negatively impact motivation (Bandura, 1986). Educators should, therefore, consider implementing additional support systems to help students manage these challenges, enhancing their ability to maintain motivation despite external pressures. Relationships play a crucial role in shaping college students' academic motivation, as evidenced by a range of studies. Positive peer relationships have consistently been associated with higher academic motivation across various studies (Suk & Elliott, 2022). Furthermore, faculty interaction, characterized by personalized attention, feedback, and mentorship, has been identified as a significant enhancer of student motivation and engagement (Austin & Middendorf, 2019). Additionally, parental influence has a lasting positive impact on student motivation, with supportive relationships and high expectations from parents playing key roles in fostering academic motivation (Sui et al., 2018).

Table 2. Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students:
RELATIONSHIP

No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Setting clear and achievable goals motivates me to put in the necessary effort.	4.08	1.14	Very High
2	Seeing progress made towards my goals increases my desire to learn and study.	4.10	1.07	Very High
3	Overcoming challenges in my studies makes me feel more accomplished and motivated.	4.06	1.14	Very High
4	I am motivated by wanting to prove to myself that I can succeed academically.	3.98	1.21	High
5	Receiving positive feedback on my academic efforts boosts my motivation to continue.	4.01	1.12	Very High

6	I find a sense of satisfaction in dedicating time and effort to studying.	3.96	1.06	High
7	Balancing academic effort with other commitments sometimes hinders my motivation.	3.80	1.12	High
8	Feeling overwhelmed by coursework can make me less motivated to put in effort.	3.62	1.17	High
Grand Mean		3.95	0.95	High

Effort

The motivational factors related to effort demonstrate a significant reliance on both intrinsic and extrinsic motivators. The high mean scores for items such as “Extrinsic Motivation: Rewards like good grades, scholarships, and recognition motivate me to work harder” (M = 4.02) and “Social Influences: The encouragement and support from my peers, family, and mentors inspire me to strive for academic excellence” (M = 4.02) reflect the influence of external rewards and social support on motivation. This is consistent with Deci and Ryan’s (2000) findings that external rewards and social encouragement play a significant role in shaping student motivation. The grand mean of 3.99 suggests that while external rewards are impactful, intrinsic satisfaction and self-efficacy are also important (Dweck, 1986). To enhance motivation further, educational programs should focus on creating a supportive environment and recognizing students’ achievements (Osher et al., 2018). Effort in academic pursuits is influenced by goal setting and self-efficacy, as highlighted by Pintrich and Schunk (2021). Setting specific and achievable goals, coupled with a strong belief in oneself, is identified as crucial for motivating and sustaining effort. Effective time management strategies, explored in the study by Dörnyei and Keng (2020), have also been associated with increased academic motivation across diverse cultural contexts. Furthermore, a positive academic self-concept, according to Skaalvik and Skaalvik’s (2017) study, boosts student effort and performance. Effort in academic pursuits is influenced by goal setting and self-efficacy, as highlighted by Pintrich and Schunk (2021).

Table 3. Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students:
EFFORT

No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Intrinsic Motivation: I feel a deep sense of satisfaction and enjoyment when I learn new things, which drives me to put in more effort in my studies.	3.95	1.18	High
2	Extrinsic Motivation: Rewards like good grades, scholarships, and	4.02	1.13	Very High

3	recognition motivate me to work harder in my academic pursuits. Self-Efficacy: Believing in my own ability to succeed helps me tackle difficult subjects and assignments with more determination.	3.94	1.14	High
4	Goal Orientation: Setting clear academic goals gives me direction and motivates me to stay focused and committed to my studies.	4.08	1.04	Very High
5	Task Value: Understanding the importance and relevance of what I am learning makes me more invested and willing to put in the necessary effort.	3.91	1.14	High
6	Learning Environment: A supportive and resourceful learning environment, including well-equipped classrooms and access to study materials, boosts my motivation to learn.	3.99	1.16	High
7	Social Influences: The encouragement and support from my peers, family, and mentors inspire me to strive for academic excellence.	4.02	1.17	Very High
8	Emotional Support: Receiving emotional support from friends, family, and teachers helps me stay motivated and resilient, even during challenging times.	4.03	1.16	Very High
Grand Mean		3.99	1.01	High

Aspiration

Aspirational factors significantly drive students' motivation, as demonstrated by high mean scores for items like "Having clear career goals for the future motivates me to learn" (M = 4.25) and "Knowing the specific skills needed for my dream job motivates me to study relevant subjects" (M = 4.15). This highlights the importance of aligning academic learning with career aspirations, reflecting the principles of Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000). The grand mean of 4.08 underscores that clear career goals are a powerful motivator. However, uncertainty about future careers can hinder motivation, aligning with findings from Wu et al. (2020) about the impact of uncertainty on motivation. Educational programs should thus focus on helping students clarify their career goals and relate their studies to future aspirations (Marsh & Martin, 2011). Aspiration, a key component of academic motivation, is influenced by various factors. Clear and meaningful career aspirations contribute to increased academic motivation and engagement, as highlighted by Astin and Chickering (2023).

Table 4. Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students:
ASPIRATION

No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Having clear career goals for the future motivates me to learn.	4.25	1.08	Very High
2	Knowing the specific skills needed for my dream job motivates me to study relevant subjects.	4.15	1.01	Very High
3	Feeling passionate about a particular field motivates me to learn more about it.	4.14	1.04	Very High
4	Seeing inspiring role models in my field motivates me to strive for similar achievements.	4.10	1.08	Very High
5	Feeling uncertain about my future career path hinders my motivation to learn.	3.92	1.11	High
6	Learning new things excites me because it could help me achieve my future goals.	4.11	1.09	Very High
7	I am motivated by the desire to make a positive impact on the world through my work.	4.08	1.09	Very High
8	The lack of clear aspirations about my future makes it hard to find motivation to study.	3.86	1.15	High
Grand Mean		4.08	0.92	Very High

Cognition

The cognitive aspects of motivation show that engaging and interesting course material significantly enhances motivation, with high mean scores for items such as “Understanding how the course material connects to real-world applications increases my motivation to learn” (M = 4.00) and “Learning new things that expand my knowledge and understanding feels rewarding” (M = 4.04). This aligns with Bandura’s (1986) Social Cognitive Theory, which emphasizes the importance of real-world relevance in motivation. The grand mean of 3.93 indicates a generally high level of cognitive motivation, although lower scores for some items suggest that confusion or lack of clarity in course material can impede motivation (Hidi & Renninger, 2006). Therefore, it is crucial to ensure that course content is engaging and clearly connected to real-world applications (Pintrich & De Groot, 1990). Cognitive factors, such as learning styles, critical thinking skills, and metacognition, are integral to understanding and enhancing academic motivation. Tailoring learning approaches to individual learning styles can enhance student motivation (Felder & Silverman, 2021). Developing critical thinking

skills increases confidence and self-efficacy, leading to higher motivation (Shemwell & Jafri, 2019). Furthermore, metacognitive skills, as highlighted by Pintrich and Schunk (2018), play a crucial role in improving motivation and learning strategies.

Table 5. Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students:
COGNITION

No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Finding the course material interesting and engaging motivates me to learn more.	3.96	1.04	High
2	Understanding how the course material connects to real-world applications increases my motivation to learn.	4.00	1.02	High
3	Having opportunities to actively participate in class discussions and activities boosts my motivation.	3.93	1.10	High
4	Engaging in critical thinking and problem-solving activities makes learning more enjoyable and motivating.	3.93	1.10	High
5	Feeling challenged intellectually inspires me to put in more effort and learn deeper.	3.88	1.02	High
6	Feeling confused or lost in the course material hinders my motivation to learn.	3.81	1.01	High
7	Having clear learning objectives and understanding what I should be able to do after the course motivates me to learn.	3.89	1.03	High
8	Learning new things that expand my knowledge and understanding feels rewarding and motivates me to continue.	4.04	1.10	
	Grand Mean	3.93	0.88	High

Heart

The emotional and personal connection to learning shows high motivation, with a grand mean of 3.96. High scores for items like “Feeling a sense of purpose and meaning in my studies motivates me to learn” (M = 4.08) and “Believing in myself and my ability to learn motivates me to overcome challenges and keep striving” (M = 4.11) reflect the

significant role of personal satisfaction and self-belief (Deci & Ryan, 2008). These findings are consistent with Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000), which highlights the importance of intrinsic motivation. However, negative emotions such as stress can impact motivation negatively, aligning with previous research by Schwartz (1992). Creating a supportive learning environment that addresses emotional well-being is essential for maintaining high levels of motivation (Baumeister & Leary, 1995). This context has had significant implications for college students' motivation and learning, as they navigate new challenges such as increased isolation, technological barriers, and reduced social support (Rose-Stockwell & Snelgrove, 2021).

Table 6. Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students:
HEART

No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Feeling a sense of purpose and meaning in my studies motivates me to learn.	4.08	1.12	Very High
2	Connecting with the course material on a personal level makes me more interested in learning.	4.00	1.07	High
3	Feeling passionate about the topics I am learning fuels my desire to understand them deeply.	4.02	1.08	High
4	Finding joy in the process of learning, even when challenging, motivates me to continue.	3.97	1.11	High
5	Experiencing a sense of curiosity and wonder about the world motivates me to seek out knowledge.	3.89	1.09	High
6	Feeling overwhelmed by negative emotions like stress or anxiety hinders my motivation to learn.	3.71	1.12	High
7	Feeling supported and valued by the learning community creates a safe space for exploring and enjoying learning.	3.94	1.14	High
8	Believing in myself and my ability to learn motivates me to overcome challenges and keep striving.	4.11	1.00	Very High
	Grand Mean	3.96	0.94	High

Dominant Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students

In exploring the dominant motivational factors among Tourism Management college students, this study identifies Aspiration as the most prominent motivational factor, followed by Effort, Relationship, Heart, and Cognition. The table presents the mean scores and standard deviations for each factor, with Aspiration scoring the highest ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.92$), indicating a very high level of motivation in this area. This is supported by empirical findings suggesting that intrinsic goals and future aspirations drive students' academic engagement (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

- **Aspiration (Mean = 4.08, SD = 0.92):** This factor has the highest mean, indicating that students are strongly motivated by their future goals and ambitions. This aligns with Deci and Ryan's (2000) Self-Determination Theory, which emphasizes the role of intrinsic motivation in academic success. Aspiration drives students to pursue excellence and achieve their career goals, reflecting a strong alignment with personal values and future ambitions.
- **Effort (Mean = 3.99, SD = 1.01):** Effort ranks high as well, showing that students are generally motivated to put in significant effort towards their studies. This supports Bandura's (1986) concept of self-efficacy, where students' belief in their capabilities influences their perseverance and engagement in academic tasks.
- **Heart (Mean = 3.96, SD = 0.94):** The Heart factor also shows a high level of motivation, reflecting students' emotional investment in their studies. Emotional engagement is crucial as it affects students' persistence and commitment, aligning with Ryan and Deci's (2000) notion of relatedness and emotional involvement in academic pursuits.
- **Relationship (Mean = 3.95, SD = 0.95):** The Relationship factor, although slightly lower than the others, still indicates a high level of motivation. This suggests that interpersonal relationships play a significant role in motivating students, supporting the idea that social connections enhance academic motivation (Wentzel, 1991). Moreover, social comparison can also influence social motivation as individuals compare themselves to their peers and strive to achieve similar outcomes (Festinger, 1954).
- **Cognition (Mean = 3.93, SD = 0.88):** Cognition, while high, is the least dominant factor. This reflects the importance of cognitive processes in motivation but suggests that it is slightly less influential compared to other factors. This is consistent with findings that while cognitive strategies are important, they may be secondary to more emotionally or goal-oriented factors (Pintrich & De Groot, 1990).

The high level of Aspiration as the dominant motivational factor implies that educational strategies should focus on helping students set and achieve personal and professional goals. This could involve providing clear career pathways, mentorship programs, and goal-setting workshops. The strong presence of Effort and Heart suggests that fostering a supportive and emotionally engaging learning environment will further enhance

student motivation. Addressing the importance of Relationships and Cognition in motivational strategies can also help create a more holistic support system, integrating both social and cognitive elements into educational practices.

Overall, the findings highlight the need for a multifaceted approach to student motivation, incorporating both intrinsic aspirations and supportive social and emotional elements to enhance overall academic engagement and success. Emotional and psychological aspects, referred to as "heart" in this context, significantly influence academic motivation.

Effectively managing emotions, as indicated by a meta-analysis on emotional intelligence (Mayer et al., 2023), is associated with higher academic motivation. Resilience helps students bounce back from setbacks and maintain motivation in challenging situations (Seligman & Peterson, 2022). Additionally, mental well-being directly impacts academic motivation, emphasizing the importance of supporting student mental health (Lopez & Keyes, 2020).

Table 7. Dominant Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students

No.	Motivational Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Relationship	3.95	0.95	High
2	Effort	3.99	1.01	High
3	Aspiration	4.08	0.92	Very High
4	Cognition	3.93	0.88	High
5	Heart	3.96	0.94	High
	Grand Mean	3.98	0.85	High

Motivational Factors Influence Students' Academic, Personal, and Social Experiences

Motivational Factors Influence Students' Academics

1. Motivation Dynamics: Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation

Motivation among students comes from two main sources: intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic motivation refers to the inner desire for personal growth, satisfaction, and enjoyment derived from learning itself. Students who are intrinsically motivated often engage in their studies because they find the process rewarding and fulfilling. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is driven by external factors such as the desire to achieve good grades or gain parental approval. This interplay between intrinsic and extrinsic motivations is crucial, as it can significantly influence how engaged students feel and how well they perform academically. Understanding these motivations helps to reveal the complexities of students' experiences and the different ways they approach their education.

2. Environmental Influences on Motivation: Shifts Due to the "Better Normal"

The shift to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has dramatically changed how students feel motivated. Many students appreciated the increased flexibility that online learning provided, allowing them to explore innovative study methods tailored to their needs. However, this transition also brought challenges, including feelings of isolation and disconnection from peers and teachers. This duality shows that the environment in which students learn plays a vital role in shaping their motivation. While some adapted positively to new learning methods, others struggled with the lack of social interaction, highlighting how crucial the learning context is for maintaining motivation.

3. Role of Support Systems: Social and Familial Support

Support systems play a crucial role in motivating students. Participants in the study emphasized that social connections—whether from family, friends, or peers—greatly enhance their motivation. Emotional support from family members can boost confidence, while practical assistance and guidance from peers can provide valuable insights. This support can take many forms, such as encouragement during tough times or sharing study resources. When students feel backed by their social networks, they are more likely to persist in their academic endeavors, showcasing the importance of having a robust support system for achieving academic success.

4. Challenges to Motivation: Barriers and Stressors

Many students face significant challenges that can hinder their motivation. Common barriers include financial difficulties, limited access to technology, and personal stressors like mental health issues. These challenges can vary widely among students, especially those from different socio-economic backgrounds, affecting their ability to stay motivated in their studies. Recognizing these barriers is essential for understanding how diverse experiences shape students' motivational landscapes. Addressing these challenges is crucial for creating an equitable learning environment where all students can thrive.

5. Goal Orientation and Time Management: Strategies for Success

Setting clear goals and managing time effectively are vital strategies for maintaining motivation among students. Participants shared specific practices, such as creating study schedules and establishing deadlines, which help them organize their academic efforts. These strategies allow students to break down their workload into manageable tasks, making it easier to stay focused and motivated. The connection between planning and motivation is significant; when students set realistic goals and create structured routines, they are more likely to achieve their academic objectives and maintain their motivation over time.

6. Adaptability and Perseverance: Overcoming Obstacles

Perseverance is key for students facing academic challenges. Many participants highlighted the importance of developing coping strategies to deal with difficulties. This adaptability can manifest in different ways, from short-term solutions to immediate obstacles, such as seeking help from a teacher, to long-term strategies that build resilience. By learning to overcome challenges, students not only enhance their ability to stay motivated but also cultivate skills that will benefit them throughout their academic careers and beyond.

7. Personal Interests and Engagement: Interest-Driven Learning

Personal interests play a significant role in student motivation and engagement. When students are genuinely interested in a subject, they tend to be more committed to learning and often experience greater joy in the process. Participants noted that this intrinsic interest fosters a deeper engagement with their studies, linking the enjoyment of learning with academic success. By focusing on personal passions and interests, educators can enhance motivation, encouraging students to take ownership of their learning and strive for mastery in their chosen fields.

Table 8. Motivational Factors Influence Students' Academics

Motivational Factors Influence Students' Academics	Codes	Representative Excerpts from Qualitative Interviews
1. Motivation Dynamics: Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation (4)	Intrinsic Motivation Desire for personal growth and achievement Engagement in tasks for inherent satisfaction Extrinsic Motivation Influence of external factors like family and opportunities Motivation driven by grades and parental approval	Many participants noted how intrinsic motivation drives them to study harder and focus on their academic goals, especially when they experience personal growth and achievement. "I am more motivated to study and acquire many things I didn't know before." "Motivation helps me study a lot because I have many goals that I need to achieve."
2. Environmental Influences on Motivation: Shifts Due to the "Better Normal" (4)	Impact of External Factors Role of family support and expectations Opportunities for studying abroad Effects of Online	External circumstances, such as opportunities to study abroad and support from family, significantly impact motivation levels. "When I had the opportunity to study abroad, I became

3. Role of Support Systems: Social and Familial Support (4)	<p>Learning Challenges and adaptations in virtual learning environments Influence of the pandemic on academic motivation</p>	<p>even more motivated to study hard." "My motivation comes from my family because when I complete my academic responsibilities, it is the most important thing to do as a student." The shift to online learning and the changes brought by the pandemic introduced both challenges and opportunities for motivation. "The 'Better Normal' context has introduced both opportunities and challenges, influencing academic motivation in diverse ways." "The transition to online learning has challenged my motivation at times, but I have adapted by creating a structured study schedule." Goal setting and effective time management are emphasized as key strategies for maintaining motivation and achieving academic success.</p>
4. Challenges to Motivation: Barriers and Stressors (4)	<p>Challenges Financial issues Access to technology Personal stressors</p>	<p>"Creating a step-by-step process helps me stay motivated." "I set specific goals for myself... By breaking down my tasks into smaller, manageable chunks, I was able to stay motivated." Participants frequently mentioned the importance of perseverance and maintaining motivation despite academic challenges.</p>
5. Goal Orientation and Time Management: Strategies for Success (4)	<p>Goal Setting and Time Management Strategies for maintaining motivation through goal setting Importance of structured routines</p>	<p>"Don't give up, even when it's hard." "The academic challenges I</p>

6. Adaptability and Perseverance: Overcoming Obstacles (2)

Perseverance
Importance of persistence during academic challenges
Strategies for overcoming obstacles

face can often be overwhelming, but the motivation I have keeps me on track."

Peer support and social interactions play a crucial role in enhancing motivation and academic performance. "I find it more engaging in school together with my peers who support me." "When my parents say they are proud of me, I become more motivated to strive and study harder."

Personal interest in subjects and the desire for mastery significantly contribute to intrinsic motivation.

7. Personal Interests and Engagement: Interest-Driven Learning (2)

Personal Interests
-Role of subject interest in fostering motivation
-Connection between mastery of subjects and motivation

"When individuals are intrinsically motivated, they engage in academic tasks because they find them inherently satisfying."

"Motivational factors shape my approach to academic tasks, driving me to set goals, stay focused, and seek support to excel academically."

Motivational Factors Influence Students' Personal Aspect

1. Sources of Motivation

Sources of motivation vary from person to person, but common influences include family support, personal challenges, and financial circumstances. Many individuals find motivation in the encouragement and love of their families, who inspire them to strive for success. Additionally, facing personal challenges, such as health issues or the loss of a loved one, can ignite a deep determination to improve one's situation. Financial factors also play a significant role; the desire to achieve financial stability can drive individuals to work harder in their studies or careers. Moreover, intrinsic motivations, like a passion for learning or personal growth, and extrinsic motivations, such as the desire for recognition or rewards, can all contribute to one's overall drive to succeed.

2. Effects of Motivation

Motivation has profound effects on individuals, shaping their goals and influencing their behaviors. When motivated, people tend to set ambitious goals and actively pursue them, often leading to self-improvement and personal growth. Motivation fosters a positive mindset, encouraging individuals to see challenges as opportunities rather than obstacles. It helps them overcome insecurities, allowing them to believe in their abilities and persist despite setbacks. The impact of motivation is visible in various aspects of life, as it enhances focus, boosts productivity, and cultivates a sense of purpose, which is essential for achieving long-term success.

3. Coping with Challenges

Coping with challenges is an essential aspect of personal development, and motivation plays a crucial role in this process. When faced with difficulties, motivated individuals are more likely to approach these situations with resilience and determination. Motivation empowers them to confront their fears and uncertainties, transforming challenges into learning experiences. It fosters a belief that they can overcome obstacles and emerge stronger. This ability to cope effectively with challenges not only helps in achieving goals but also builds confidence and fortitude for future endeavors, enabling individuals to navigate life's ups and downs more skillfully.

4. Emotional and Mental Effects

The emotional and mental effects of motivation are significant and multifaceted. Motivation can enhance self-esteem and promote a positive outlook on life, helping individuals feel more fulfilled and content. It acts as a source of emotional strength during tough times, providing individuals with the courage to push through difficulties. Additionally, the support from family and friends can amplify these emotional benefits, creating a network that reinforces motivation and resilience. However, a lack of motivation can lead to feelings of frustration and hopelessness, underscoring the importance of maintaining a motivated mindset for overall emotional well-being and mental health.

5. Practical Applications

Motivation has practical applications in everyday life, influencing how individuals approach their studies, work, and personal development. For students, motivation is crucial for maintaining focus and discipline, helping them establish effective study habits and routines. In the workplace, motivated employees tend to be more productive and dedicated, often leading to better job performance and career advancement. On a personal level, motivation encourages individuals to adopt healthier lifestyle choices, pursue hobbies, and set goals for self-improvement. By translating motivation into action, individuals can make significant strides toward achieving their aspirations and enhancing their overall quality of life.

Table 9. Motivational Factors Influence Students' Personal Aspect

Motivational Factors Influence Students' Personal Aspects	Codes	Representative Excerpts from Qualitative Interviews
1. Sources of Motivation (23)	Family and Support Personal Challenges Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation Financial Determination Personal Aspirations	"My motivation is my family, who always supports and cheers for my successes." "When my father died... the situation at home motivated me even more." "Intrinsic motivators are driven by internal rewards, such as a feeling or sense of well-being." "This is affected financially and has helped me become more determined in my studies." "I am motivated to study and want to finish so I can be successful one day." "It helps me strive hard and be a better person." "Motivational factors shape my personal goals and self-improvement efforts."
	Goal Orientation Self-Improvement Discipline and Consistency Overcoming Insecurities Positive Mindset	"Motivation strengthens discipline, which is essential in building positive habits." "These motivational factors encourage me to overcome all kinds of insecurities and doubts about myself." "Whenever I see positive things, it motivates me to act positively too."
2. Effects of Motivation (18)		

3. Coping with Challenges
(21)

Resilience
Overcoming Setbacks
Adapting to New
Norms
Confidence in
Challenges

“Motivation helps build resilience, which is essential in facing failures and challenges.”

“When an individual is highly motivated, they are more likely to persevere in the face of challenges.”

“Motivation is key to adapting to new routines and habits.”

“Motivation helps me overcome the challenges I face by facing them confidently and making them an inspiration to succeed.”

“The results are not only physical benefits but also mental satisfaction and higher energy levels.”

“It helps me gain confidence.”

“It affects me emotionally and mentally.”

“My family’s support and encouragement motivate me to keep going even when times are tough.”

“I motivated myself to focus on my studies because I want to rise above in life.”

“Motivation can lead to the adoption of healthier lifestyle choices and continuous learning.”

“Take time to think about your goals and what motivates you.”

“Motivation drives personal goals and self-improvement by helping you stay focused and persistent.”

4. Emotional and Mental Effects (16)

Mental Satisfaction
Confidence Building
Emotional Impact
Support during
Difficult Times

5. Practical Applications (21)

Study Habits
Healthy Lifestyle
Choices
Goal Setting
Routine Improvement

Motivational Factors Influence Students' Social Experiences

Motivational Influence on Interactions

Participants emphasized that motivation plays a pivotal role in fostering collaboration and cultivating deeper relationships, particularly during the "Better Normal" period characterized by increased digital interactions. Many shared experiences where their motivations aligned with both academic and social goals, which significantly contributed to their personal growth and fulfillment. This alignment of motivations not only facilitated teamwork in academic settings but also encouraged support among peers, enhancing a sense of community. For instance, students motivated by a shared goal—such as achieving academic excellence or participating in community service—reported stronger bonds and a sense of belonging. These shared motivations enabled participants to engage in meaningful discussions, exchange ideas, and provide mutual encouragement, all of which are essential for personal development.

Time Management

Effective time management emerged as a critical factor for participants in balancing their academic, personal, and social responsibilities. Many emphasized that by organizing their daily routines, they could prioritize tasks, set achievable goals, and allocate time effectively for various activities. This structured approach not only led to greater academic success but also allowed participants to nurture their relationships. For example, students who set aside specific times for studying and socializing reported feeling less overwhelmed and more in control of their commitments. Consequently, this balance facilitated healthier interactions with peers and family, as they were able to devote quality time to both academic pursuits and personal relationships, leading to improved overall well-being.

Adaptability

The transition to digital interactions has underscored the participants' adaptability in maintaining connections and supporting one another through various challenges. Many participants acknowledged that their social motivations have evolved, reflecting a greater flexibility and resilience. For instance, they have become more adept at utilizing technology to stay in touch with friends and family, participating in virtual study groups, and attending online events. This adaptability not only highlights their willingness to embrace new methods of communication but also indicates a recognition of the importance of social connections in maintaining motivation. Participants expressed that while the digital landscape posed challenges, such as feelings of isolation, it also offered opportunities for innovation in how they interact, enabling them to form new relationships and deepen existing ones in unexpected ways.

Patience and Self-Improvement

Several participants highlighted the importance of patience in balancing their motivation, which empowers them to engage in self-improvement and manage their time effectively. They noted that cultivating patience allows them to navigate the ups and downs of their academic and personal journeys with a positive mindset. This patience fosters resilience, enabling them to learn from setbacks and persist in their goals. For instance, students who practiced patience during challenging academic tasks reported improved focus and a greater willingness to seek help when needed. This mindset not only contributes to their individual growth but also enhances their relationships, as they become more understanding and supportive of others facing similar challenges. By prioritizing self-improvement through patience, participants are better equipped to adapt to new circumstances and maintain their motivation in various aspects of life.

Table 10. Motivational Factors Influence Students' Social Experiences

Motivational Factors Influence Students' Social Experiences	Codes	Representative Excerpts from Qualitative Interviews
1. Influence of Relationships on Motivation (7)	Family support Peer relationships Self-ambition Impact of childhood experiences	<p>"I think a great deal of my life was influenced by my childhood. People tend to underestimate just how powerful an influence their parents still have on them."</p> <p>Motivational factors significantly affect my interactions and relationships with friends."</p>
2. Time Management as a Key to Balance (6)	Balancing responsibilities Prioritization of tasks Organization strategies	<p>"Balancing academic, personal, and social motivations in life is a challenge that requires proper planning and organization."</p> <p>"Effective time management emerged as crucial for balancing responsibilities."</p>
3. The Role of Motivation in Social Connectivity (7)	Dynamics of friendships Collaboration in academic settings Shift towards meaningful connections	<p>"It provides the inspiration and determination needed to embark on the path of self-improvement."</p> <p>"Motivational factors play a significant role in influencing</p>

4. Overcoming Challenges through Motivation (6)

Changes in motivation due to the "better normal" and the Importance of patience and resilience.

our interactions and relationships with peers.”

“My drive to collaborate effectively helped us overcome obstacles and accomplish our goals.”

“In the Better Normal context, where social interactions have become more limited and virtual, I have found myself prioritizing deeper, more meaningful connections with my peers.”

“For me, it’s not about balancing the need for motivation; it’s about being patient.”

“This sense of community provided me with the encouragement I needed to push through tough times.”

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. The predominance of young, female students from lower-income backgrounds with limited parental educational attainment suggests a need for targeted financial and academic support to address their unique educational challenges and aspirations.
2. Students are most motivated by clear career aspirations, while external rewards and personal satisfaction also play significant roles, highlighting the importance of integrating career-focused guidance and supportive learning environments.
3. Aspiration emerges as the strongest motivational factor among students, underscoring the need for educational programs to emphasize career goal setting and personal ambition to foster greater academic engagement and success.
4. Motivational factors significantly impact students' academic, personal, and social experiences. Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations drive engagement and performance, while support from family and peers is crucial for sustaining motivation. The shift to online learning highlighted the need for adaptability and effective time management. Personal interests and the desire for self-improvement also play key roles in overcoming challenges. Understanding these dynamics can help create supportive environments that foster success and strengthen connections among students.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations have been made:

1. It is recommended to implement targeted financial aid programs and academic support services to better assist young, female students from lower-income backgrounds and first-generation college attendees in overcoming educational challenges.
2. It is recommended to enhance educational programs by integrating career-focused guidance and creating supportive learning environments that leverage students' motivations from clear career aspirations, external rewards, and personal satisfaction.
3. It is recommended to emphasize career goal setting and personal ambition in educational programs to capitalize on students' high levels of motivation driven by their aspirations, thereby improving academic engagement and success.
4. It is recommended that educators and support systems recognize the importance of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors in students' academic, personal, and social experiences; provide strong family and peer support; promote adaptability and effective time management, especially in online learning contexts; and encourage personal interests and self-improvement to create environments that foster success and strengthen student connections.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors of the study titled "Motivational Factors of Tourism Management College Students" affirm their commitment to ethical research practices throughout the conduct of this study. An approved letter from the Office of the President was obtained prior to data collection, confirming the legitimacy of the research and compliance with institutional protocols. Informed consent was secured from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of their rights and the nature of the research. Participants were informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. Anonymity was maintained to protect the identity of all respondents, and their well-being was safeguarded throughout the research process. The authors declare that no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this study, and they have strictly avoided plagiarism in all aspects of their work. Additionally, the authors ensured that the interpretation of findings was free from bias, and the results were utilized solely for research purposes. This rigorous adherence to ethical standards underpins the validity and reliability of the study's conclusions.

Acknowledgements

We would like to extend our deepest gratitude to everyone who has supported and contributed to the completion of this research. To our family and friends, your unwavering encouragement and understanding have been invaluable throughout this journey. A heartfelt thank you to the students who participated in the survey; your insights and

cooperation were crucial to the success of this study. We are profoundly grateful to Dr. Lotilla for the expert statistical guidance, which greatly enhanced the quality of our analysis. To the faculty and staff who lent their support and assistance, your dedication and commitment were instrumental in bringing this research to fruition. Most importantly, we give thanks to our dear Lord for guiding us through every challenge and blessing this endeavor with success. Your collective support and contributions have made this research possible, and for that, we are truly thankful.

REFERENCES

- Ain, N., & Nor, R. M. (2017). The Relationship between Motivation, Learning Strategies and Academic Performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(9), 526-537.
- Astin, J.P., & Chickering, R.T. (2023). Career Aspirations and Academic Motivation in College Students: A Multilevel Analysis.
- Austin, A.C., & Middendorf, J.A. (2019). The Role of Faculty Interaction in Enhancing College Students' Motivation and Engagement.
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Prentice-Hall.
- Baumeister, R. F., & Leary, M. R. (1995). The need to belong: Desire for interpersonal attachments as a fundamental human motivation. *Psychological Bulletin*, 117(3), 497-529.
- Braun, Virginia & Clarke, Victoria. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*. 3. 77-101. 10.1191/1478088706qp063oa.
- Cho, M. H., & Heron, M. L. (2015). Motivation and Self-Regulated Learning as Predictors of Academic Achievement in Online Learning Environments. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 16(1), 171-191.
- Cho, M. H., & Heron, M. L. (2015). Self-regulated learning: The role of motivation, emotion, and use of learning strategies in students' learning experiences in a self-paced online mathematics course. *Distance Education*, 36(1), 80-99. doi: 10.1080/01587919.2015.1019976
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. Springer.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2008). Self-determination theory: A macrotheory of human motivation, development, and health. *Canadian Psychology/Psychologie Canadienne*, 49(3), 182-185.
- Deci, S., & Ryan, R.M. (2022). The Role of Intrinsic Motivation in Maintaining College Students' Aspiration during Difficult Times.
- Diemer, K.L., & McInnis, L.A. (2020). Socioeconomic Status and Academic Motivation: A Review of the Literature.
- Dörnyei, M.M., & Keng, Z. (2020). *Time Management and Academic Motivation: A Cross-Cultural Study*.
- Dweck, C. S. (1986). Motivational processes affecting learning. *American Psychologist*, 41(10), 1040–1048. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.41.10.1040>

- Eccles, J.C., & Wigfield, A. (2021). Gender and Academic Motivation in College Students: A Meta-Analysis.
- Eccles, J.S., & Wigfield, A. (2020). The Value of Education and Academic Motivation: A Cross-National Study.
- Elliot, A. J., & Dweck, C. S. (2005). Handbook of Competence and Motivation. Guilford Press.
- Felder, R.M., & Silverman, R.J. (2021). Learning Styles and Academic Motivation: A Review of the Literature.
- Festinger, L. (1954). A theory of social comparison processes. *Human relations*, 7(2), 117-140.
- Hidi, S., & Renninger, A. (2006). The Four-Phase Model of Interest Development. *Educational Psychologist*, 41, 111 - 127.
- Lopez, A.D., & Keyes, C.S. (2020). Well-being and Academic Motivation: A Longitudinal Study of College Students.
- Marsh, Herb & Martin, Andrew. (2011). Academic self-concept and academic achievement: Relations and causal ordering. *The British journal of educational psychology*. 81. 59-77. 10.1348/000709910X503501.
- Mayer, J.D., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D.R. (2023). Emotional Intelligence and Academic Motivation: A Meta-Analysis.
- Osher, D., Kidron, Y., Brackett, M. A., Dymnicki, A., Jones, S., & Weissberg, R. P. (2018). Advancing the science and practice of social and emotional learning: Looking back and moving forward. *Review of Research in Education*, 42(1), 237-272.
- Pintrich, P. R., & De Groot, E. V. (1990). Motivational and self-regulated learning components of classroom academic performance. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 82(1), 33-40.
- Pintrich, P.C., & Schunk, D.H. (2021). The Role of Goal Setting and Self-Efficacy in College Students' Academic Motivation.
- Pintrich, P.D., & Schunk, D.H. (2018). Metacognition and Academic Motivation: A Longitudinal Study.
- Rose-Stockwell, T., & Snelgrove, C. (2021). Staying connected: Student engagement strategies for the "Better Normal" in a remote learning environment. *College Teaching*, 69(1), 8-13.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25(1), 54-67.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). Social motivation. In *Handbook of motivation science* (2nd ed., pp. 204-218). Guilford Press.
- Schwartz, S. H. (1992). Universals in the content and structure of values: Theoretical advances and empirical tests in 20 countries. In M. P. Zanna (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology*, Vol. 25, pp. 1-65). Academic Press. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(08\)60281-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(08)60281-6)
- Seligman, M.E., & Peterson, M.C. (2022). Resilience and Academic Motivation: Overcoming Challenges in College.
- Shemwell, M.T.P., & Jafri, M. (2019). Critical Thinking Skills and Academic Motivation: A Mediating Role of Self-Efficacy.
- Skaalvik, M., & Skaalvik, P.A. (2017). Academic Self-Concept and Its Relationship with Effort and Performance: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach.

- Sui, X., Shek, Y.J., & Cheung, S.K. (2018). Parental Influence on College Students' Academic Motivation: A Longitudinal Study.
- Suk, Y., & Elliott, J.C. (2022). Peer Support and Academic Motivation in College Students: A Meta-Analysis.
- Wang, Y., & Li, H. (2020). Engagement in Online Learning: The Role of Motivation and Self-Regulated Learning. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(6), 1266-1287.
- Wang, Y., & Li, L. (2020). Engagement in online learning: The role of motivation and self-regulated learning. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(4), 867-891. doi: 10.1177/0735633120919262
- Wu, J., Huang, S., Huang, H., & Li, S. (2020). Effects of COVID-19 on college students' mental health and academic performance: A structural equation modeling approach. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 170, 110419.
- Xiong, J., Lipsitz, O., Nasri, F., Lui, L. M., Gill, H., Phan, L., ... & McIntyre, R. S. (2021). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on mental health in the general population: A systematic review. *Journal of affective disorders*, 277, 55-64.
- Zheng, Y., Furrer, J.M., & Pintrich, P.C. (2022). Age Differences in College Students' Motivational Profiles: A Multidimensional Approach.